

An approach to geometric optimization of railway catenaries

Santiago Gregori^a, Manuel Tur^a, Enrique Nadal^a, Francisco Javier Fuenmayor^a,

^aCentro de Investigación en Ingeniería Mecánica,

Departamento de Ingeniería Mecánica y de Materiales, Universitat Politècnica de València,

Camino de Vera s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain

December 11, 2017

Abstract

The quality of current collection becomes a limiting factor when the aim is to increase the speed of the present railway systems. In this work an attempt is made to improve current collection quality optimizing catenary geometry by means of a Genetic Algorithm. As contact wire height and dropper spacing are thought to be highly influential parameters, they are chosen as the optimization variables. The results obtained show that a Genetic Algorithm can be used to optimize catenary geometry to improve current collection quality measured in terms of the standard deviation of the contact force. Furthermore, it is highlighted that apart from the usual pre-sag, other geometric parameters should also be taken into account when designing railway catenaries.

1. Introduction

The overhead equipment, commonly named the catenary, is the system in charge of providing the energy supply to the electric railway vehicle by means of a sliding contact with

the pantograph, which is a mechanism located on top of the locomotive. The interaction force between the pantograph and the catenary contact wire determines the quality of the supply. High contact forces can cause excessive wear on the sliding surfaces, while too weak forces may lead to contact losses and sparking, which apart from the damage it can cause, it interrupts the energy provision.

As the maximum speed of commercial railways is mainly limited by the pantograph-catenary interaction [1,2], an appropriate design (the reader is referred to [3] for a wide overview of the design of overhead contact lines) is crucial for the correct behavior of such a system. This explains why in recent years a lot of effort has been put into developing accurate models capable of simulating the dynamic pantograph-catenary interaction. Among the vast diversity of studies found in the literature, the benchmark [4] and the references therein deserve special attention for the insight they provide into the present state of the art.

According to [4], Finite Element Method (FEM) and lumped mass models are the most frequently used approaches to model the catenary and the pantograph systems, respectively. Euler Bernoulli beam elements are commonly employed to model the catenary wires. However, in this work we have chosen the Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation (ANCF) [5]. The contact between the pantograph and the contact wire is mostly dealt with by a penalty method, although some other approaches such as kinematic constraints may be also used to this end.

This work is aimed at optimizing the catenary in terms of current collection quality. This quality can be quantified by the standard deviation of the interaction force, which defines the objective function to be minimized. Current collection quality is influenced by many parameters, such as the stiffness and damping of the pan-head and frame, the contact wire tension or the static uplift force, whose influence on the contact force is thoroughly analyzed in [6]. Some optimizations are found in the literature concerning the parameters which define the pantograph model. In [7] a robust design technique was used to find the optimal lumped parameters for the best current collection in catenaries with variable span lengths. By optimizing the stiffness, damping and mass values of the pantograph lumped model, the standard deviation of the contact force was reduced by 11% in [8], where a Genetic Algorithm (GS) was used. A 9% of reduction was achieved in [9] using a differential evolutionary algorithm. Similar improvements are found in [10] with the use

of pneumatic head suspensions instead of the classical mechanical systems.

Apart from the above mentioned parameters, the amount of initial sag (pre-sag) given to the contact wire also seems to be a key factor in current collection quality. Its influence on the pantograph-catenary dynamics was studied in [11]. One of the main conclusions drawn from this work is that pre-sag does not improve current collection quality in the high-speed range, where the process is dominated by wave propagation rather than the stiffness variation in the catenary. In [12] the limitations of pre-sag in improving the current collection quality were also revealed. This scenario suggests it would be advisable to follow other approaches to find better catenaries, such as setting the appropriate number of droppers and their spacing, which have been practically ignored in the literature and can also affect the interaction force [13].

The present study is, up to the authors knowledge, the first attempt in finding the optimal catenary geometry, in terms of current collection quality, by exploring alternatives such as the contact wire height profile and dropper spacing. Two catenary topologies are analyzed, namely, with and without a stitch wire. The catenary system is modeled by the Finite Element Method (FEM) and a lumped-parameters representation is used to model the pantograph.

When planning an optimization, the chosen procedure is of crucial importance. Optimization methods are mainly divided into two groups [14]: gradient-based and metaheuristic methods. Gradient-based methods need the computation of the derivatives of the objective function with respect to the optimization variables. The problem dealt with in this work is a dynamic problem with a moving load and unilateral non-linearities. In this case the calculation of these derivatives would be cumbersome and therefore, metaheuristic techniques [15], such as Genetic Algorithms, have been considered for the problem at hand with the addition of some operational restrictions.

The paper is organized as follows: after this brief introduction, all the mathematical models used to describe the whole system are explained in Section 2. The initial configuration problem of the catenary is treated in Section 3, while Section 4 is devoted to explain the dynamic interaction problem, which is solved efficiently. These three sections are included for the sake of completeness since they provide a summary of the models presented in [16], the shape-finding problem solved in [17] and the time integration procedure pro-

posed in [18], respectively. The optimization problem is set in Section 5, together with the Genetic Algorithm used to solve it. The results obtained from these optimizations are given in Section 6 for both catenary topologies. Finally, the main conclusions drawn from this work are offered in Section 7.

2. Catenary, pantograph and interaction models

The FE technique is the most widely used to model high-speed railway catenaries as can be seen from the review [19] and references in [4]. The catenary is mainly composed of a messenger wire, a contact wire, steady arms, droppers and some typologies also have stitch wires as can be seen in Fig. 1. In this work, the messenger and the contact wires are modeled by beam elements based on the Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation (ANCF), which account for axial and bending deformations, and they are identified as ‘cable elements’ throughout this paper. This type of element was first proposed by Shabana [5] and adapted for thin beams and cables in [20]. Unlike other beam formulations, ANCF elements use absolute positions and their gradients as degrees of freedom instead of rotations [17]. Bar elements are used to model droppers, steady arms and stitch wires, since they only transmit axial forces.

Figure 1: *Finite element catenary model.*

The reference and deformed configurations for a cable element are schematically represented in Fig. 2. In order to guarantee C^1 continuity, standard Hermite elements are used in which the length of the undeformed element l_{ref}^c is present.

Figure 2: Reference and deformed configurations of the ANCF element.

The degrees of freedom of bar elements are only composed of the absolute positions of the two nodes of the element, so that a linear interpolation is enough to ensure the required C^0 continuity, since bending deformations are not taken into account.

A wide variety of solutions can be found to model pantographs [10]. Due to its simplicity, a linear lumped-parameters model is used in this work. It only introduces three vertical degrees of freedom, as shown in the scheme depicted in Fig. 3a. F_p represents the force exerted by the uplift mechanism, which acts on the lower mass of the pantograph. This force should not be confused with the static uplift force in the contact between the pan head and the contact wire, which is obtained by solving the dynamic interaction problem.

A penalty method is considered to model the pantograph-catenary interaction. A scheme of this interaction is shown in Fig. 3b. In this model, a spring element with high stiffness, $k_h = 50000$ N/m, relates the vertical degrees of freedom of the cable element, which models the contact wire, with the pantograph upper mass. The interaction force is obtained by multiplying k_h by the interpenetration, i.e.:

$$f_{inter} = \begin{cases} k_h(z_1 - z_{cw}) & \text{if } z_1 - z_{cw} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } z_1 - z_{cw} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where z_1 and z_{cw} are the absolute vertical position of the upper mass of the pantograph and the interaction point on the contact wire, respectively.

Figure 3: (a) *Pantograph* and (b) *interaction model schemes*.

3. Initial configuration problem

The initial configuration or ‘shape-finding’ problem, consists of finding the position of each node along with the non-deformed length of each element in the mesh which fulfills both the static equilibrium equations and the constraints imposed by the stringing process. Due to the large displacements undergone by the cabling this is a non-linear problem. Despite the approach and the solution procedure are thoroughly explained in [17], some insights are given here.

Following the previous reference, the static equilibrium problem is defined by means of the non-linear equation:

$$\mathbf{F}_{int}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e) + \mathbf{F}_g(\mathbf{l}_{ref}^e) = 0 \quad (2)$$

along with the appropriate essential boundary conditions. The internal forces \mathbf{F}_{int} depend on the nodal coordinates \mathbf{q} as well as the reference lengths of the elements \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e , while the gravitational forces \mathbf{F}_g only depend on the latter. For a given element’s length, \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e , Eq. (2) can be solved by using for example the Newton-Raphson method, in order to obtain the static equilibrium position of the system.

However, the final static equilibrium position of the cabling must fulfill certain constraints apart from the force equilibrium. Certain elements such as those modeling the messenger wire, contact wire and stitch wire, are pre-stressed with a tension of value T . In a given

element e , this constraint can be described as:

$$c_I(\mathbf{q}, l_{ref}) = (f_{int_x}^e)^2 + (f_{int_y}^e)^2 + (f_{int_z}^e)^2 - T^2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $(f_{int_j}^e)$ is the j component of the internal nodal force vector. Other constraints such as the contact wire height, and the horizontal position of droppers, stitch wires, steady arms and mast supports, are imposed by means of the constraint equation:

$$c_{II}(\mathbf{q}) = q_i - P = 0 \quad (4)$$

where q_i for $i = x, y, z$ is the nodal coordinate enforced to have a value of P .

Putting equilibrium equations (2) and constraints $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e)$ together results in the non-linear system of algebraic equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e) &= 0 \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

which can be solved by the Newton-Raphson method, obtaining the nodal absolute positions \mathbf{q} and the initial length of each element \mathbf{l}_{ref}^e , which fulfill the restrictions imposed for the catenary stringing.

4. Dynamic interaction problem

The dynamic interaction problem needs to be solved many times during the optimization procedure, so that is crucial to have an efficient strategy in terms of computational cost to deal with this issue. The fast solution method presented in [18] is employed in this work. As pointed out in [18], apart from alleviating computational cost, the solution given by this method is just as accurate as that obtained with a classical FEM approach. In what follows, we summarize the main features of this method.

The pantograph-catenary dynamic interaction is governed by small displacements, therefore the linear system of differential equations:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} \quad (6)$$

is suitable for modeling the whole behavior of the system [18]. The stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is obtained from linearization of dynamic equation at the static equilibrium position resulting from solving Eq (5). \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{C} , are the mass and damping matrices of the whole system respectively. All these three matrices contain both the pantograph and the catenary contributions. \mathbf{F} is the vector of applied external forces, and \mathbf{u} denotes the displacements of the pantograph-catenary with respect to its static equilibrium configuration. The proportional Rayleigh damping model stated in [4], with the constants $\alpha = 0.0125$ and $\beta = 10^{-4}$, is considered in Eq. (6) for all the catenaries studied. This ordinary differential equation can be solved by using any time integration scheme such as the commonly used Newmark method. In order to obtain the displacements of the actual time step t , given the solution in the previous time step, \mathbf{u}^{t-1} , the algebraic system of equations:

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{u}^t = \mathbf{F}_{kn}^t(\mathbf{u}^{t-1}) + \mathbf{F}_{dr}^t(\mathbf{u}^t) + \mathbf{F}_{inter}^t(\mathbf{u}^t) \quad (7)$$

must be solved. Matrix $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ is obtained by applying the Newmark time discretization to Eq. (6), (see [18]). \mathbf{F}_{kn}^t is the vector of known forces, which depends on information of the previous time step. Additionally, we have moved to the right hand side of the system the force \mathbf{F}_{dr}^t necessary to compensate the slackened droppers and the interaction force \mathbf{F}_{inter}^t between the pan head and the contact wire. Note that Eq. (7) is a non-linear system since the following non-linearities are considered: i) dropper slackening, which means that droppers only work in tension and, ii) contact loss between the pantograph and the contact wire, leading to a null interaction force.

As said above, in order to speed up the calculations, the approach proposed in [18] is fully adopted. This method is based on two fundamental ideas. The first idea was originally proposed in [21] and successfully used in [22]. It consists of moving the non-linear correction forces of the slackened droppers, \mathbf{F}_{dr}^t , and also the non-linear terms involving the interaction force, \mathbf{F}_{inter}^t , to the right hand side of the system as shown in Eq. (7). In this way, the matrix $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ does not change in time and can be pre-computed and factorized only once in the algorithm.

The second idea of the method relies on the superposition principle. The displacements \mathbf{u}^t at each time step can be computed as the sum of the displacements produced by the

three terms present on the right hand side of Eq. (7), i.e.:

$$\mathbf{u}^t = \mathbf{u}_{kn}^t + \mathbf{u}_{dr}^t + \mathbf{u}_{inter}^t \quad (8)$$

To obtain the so-called known term, \mathbf{u}_{kn}^t (which is dependent on information from the previous time step, i.e. it accounts for the initial conditions), it is necessary to solve the global size system:

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}}\mathbf{u}_{kn}^t = \mathbf{F}_{kn}^t \quad (9)$$

However, the other two contributions to the total displacement at time step t can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{dr}^t &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sdr}^t} {}_i\mathbf{u}_{dr}^{*t} {}_i f_{dr}^t \\ \mathbf{u}_{inter}^t &= \mathbf{u}_{inter}^{*t} f_{inter}^t \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where ${}_i\mathbf{u}_{dr}^{*t}$ is the catenary displacement vector produced by a unitary compressive force applied on the ends of the slackened dropper i , and N_{sdr}^t is the total number of slackened droppers time step t . \mathbf{u}_{inter}^{*t} are the displacements produced by a unitary force applied upwards on the contact wire at the corresponding interaction point at time step t .

All these displacements produced by unitary forces can be pre-computed and stored. Therefore, at each time step, slackened droppers and loss of contact are checked and a small-sized non-linear problem is solved iteratively, in which the values of the slackened droppers' correction forces, ${}_i f_{dr}^t$, and the interaction force, f_{inter}^t , are the unknowns.

To sum up, the unilateral constraints of the system are iteratively dealt with in a non-linear system composed of only $N_{sdr}^t + 1$ equations. This makes the approach highly efficient, requiring a low computational cost to simulate the pantograph-catenary dynamic interaction with no further simplification hypothesis other than those assumed in the classic FEM approach. The only disadvantage that should be mentioned is the need for enough available RAM memory to avoid swapping data on the hard disk, which would slowdown the calculations. Even so, it is not a big deal because 2.5 GB is a large enough memory to store the pre-computed variables for the cases discussed here.

5. Optimization problem

As pointed out in the introduction, the main goal of this paper is to seek the best catenary geometry in terms of current collection quality. Among other parameters, the quotient between standard deviation and mean interaction force $\sigma(f_{inter})/\bar{f}_{inter}$ is thought to be a representative statistical parameter to characterize the quality of the interaction [8]. The standard [23] sets this parameter below 0.3, which guarantees less than a 1% probability of contact loss. This standard also establishes that the maximum mean contact force applied to the contact wire must fulfill the relationship:

$$\bar{f}_{inter} \leq 0.0097v^2 + 70 \quad (11)$$

for an alternating current catenary, where $200 < v < 320$ km/h. In this work, the interaction force is low-pass filtered at 20 Hz. Although it is well known that the high frequency content has an influence on the dynamic performance of the system [10, 21, 24], we decided to stick to standard EN50367 [23] and apply the filtering in order to obtain comparable results to those of [4].

The interaction force is a magnitude that varies in time and depends on many factors such as train speed, catenary geometry, material properties and so on. In this work, the train speed, the mean contact force, the pantograph model and the wire tensions remain constant, while the geometrical parameters related to droppers (length or spacing) are considered as the optimization variables for minimizing $\sigma(f_{inter})$.

Generally, denoting as \mathbf{p} the set of parameters with respect to which it is desired to optimize the catenary, the optimization problem reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}} \quad & \sigma(f_{inter}^t(\mathbf{p})) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \\ & p_i^{min} \leq p_i \leq p_i^{max} \quad i = 1, \dots, N_p \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where p_i^{min} and p_i^{max} are the lower and upper bounds of each parameter, respectively. To evaluate the objective function it is necessary to solve both the initial configuration problem (5) and the dynamic interaction problem (6). Obtaining the proper mean contact

force value given by Eq. (11) means the dynamic simulation must be repeated and the uplift force, F_p , modified according to the ratio between the prescribed value and the mean contact force obtained in the current simulation. With only two or three re-runs the target value was achieved in all cases with acceptable accuracy. As pointed out above, the problem (12) is set for a single train speed v , which simplifies the calculations but means that the optimal geometry obtained needs to be checked for other train speeds.

Generally, two main groups of solvers are suitable for solving an optimization problem: those based on the gradient and the so-called metaheuristic methods, among which Genetic Algorithms (GA) are found. The latter group of solvers was chosen in this work because a gradient-based method would require computing the derivatives of the objective function with respect to the optimization variables \mathbf{p} , which could be cumbersome for this dynamic problem with high non-linearities. On the other hand, GAs try to reproduce the stochastic process of natural selection, obtaining the global optimum even for non-linear or discontinuous objective functions, which makes them a very attractive option.

The GA used in the present study is the one included in MATLAB® software. For a problem of N_p optimization variables (for example N_p dropper lengths), the population size n is chosen (i.e. n different combinations of dropper lengths). The variables are taken as discrete in order to make a finite size space of variables.

Figure 4: *Scheme of the next generation creation process.*

An initial population evolves towards better solutions from generation to generation following the principles of natural selection, crossover and mutation (see Fig.4). A stochastic uniform process of selection was selected. The three best-scored parents were considered as elite and were moved directly to the next generation. A crossover fraction of 0.8 has

been set, which means that 80% of the children came from a random combination of parent parameters. The rest of the children were randomly obtained by mutation of the parameters of a single parent.

The algorithm runs until a certain stop criterion is accomplished. Specifically, the calculations stop when the average cumulative change in value of the objective function over a certain number of generations is less than a prescribed tolerance.

During the optimization procedure, some combination of parameters \mathbf{p} could produce non-desirable catenaries from a practical point of view. In these cases, individuals that fulfill one of the following conditions are excluded from the population:

- Contact losses were not allowed, whereby the interaction force must be positive at any time t . If a contact loss is detected the individual is not valid any more.
- All the droppers must be in tension in the static equilibrium configuration. If certain dropper d is slackened in the static equilibrium position, this catenary is no longer admissible.

It is important to emphasize that any other restriction, such as the steady arm uplift, could be incorporated into the previous list without any further consideration.

6. Numerical results

The numerical results presented in this work have been obtained from two different catenary models, which are depicted in Fig. 5. The first catenary is thoroughly described in the Benchmark [4] (B), along with the pantograph model associated with it. Unlike this model, the second catenary (SW), has stitch wires at the support locations. The geometric and material properties of this catenary model and the pantograph paired with it are listed in Appendix A. The Benchmark catenary has a pre-sag of 1/1000 the span length, i.e. 55 mm. The contact wire of the SW catenary remains horizontally without any static sag. Both models are composed of 20 spans and are used as reference catenaries for comparison purposes with the optimized configurations.

Figure 5: (a) Benchmark catenary and (b) SW catenary models.

All the dynamic simulations are carried out with a time step of 1 ms and the Newmark time integration constants are set as $\gamma = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.25$. The contact or interaction force is measured on the 10 central spans in order to avoid boundary effects. In order to meet the standards guidelines [25], which are also followed in [4], this force is low-pass filtered at 20 Hz. A velocity of $v = 300$ km/h is considered to be the design train speed for both catenaries, which implies a mean contact interaction force $\bar{f}_{inter} = 157.3$ N as given by Eq. (11). After performing a dynamic interaction simulation, the reference Benchmark catenary presents a $\sigma_B = 40$ N, while the standard deviation of the interaction force for the reference SW catenary is $\sigma_{SW} = 22.3$ N.

In what follows, Subsection 6.1 contains a test of the optimization algorithm carried out by optimizing the pre-sag. Subsections 6.2 and 6.3 are devoted to find the best topologies of the Benchmark and the SW catenaries, respectively, i.e. the contact wire height and the dropper spacing which provide the best dynamic behavior for current collection quality purposes. Finally, in Subsection 6.4 the optimized catenaries are analyzed in terms of

their static and dynamic behavior.

6.1. Pre-sag optimization

The so-called pre-sag is the contact wire sag in the static equilibrium configuration. Pre-sag is established in order to mitigate the difference in stiffness between the center of the span and the supports. Several dynamic problems with different pre-sag have been solved for both catenaries. As shown in Fig. 6, the amount of pre-sag strongly influences the standard deviation of the interaction force σ in the 10 central spans. For a given train speed, large values of pre-sag and also negative sags adversely affect the current collection quality for both the Benchmark (squares) and the SW (circles) catenaries.

Figure 6: Pre-sag optimization for a train speed $v = 300$ km/h.

In order to test the Genetic Algorithm (GA), an optimization of the pre-sag at $v = 300$ km/h is carried out. In this academic example, there is only one optimization variable, therefore only 8 generations with a population of 15 individuals are enough for the GA to find the global minimum. Optimal pre-sag is highlighted for both catenaries in Fig. 6 by a cross, in which good agreement with the expected values is observed. This optimal value matches with the reference SW model, which has no initial sag. However, the pre-sag Benchmark catenary is far from the optimal values at the speed of 300 km/h.

Figure 7: Evolution of the (a) optimal pre-sag and (b) minimum and reference contact force σ , with respect to the train speed.

The optimal pre-sag is thought to be strongly affected by train speed. To investigate this relation, some optimizations are carried out at velocities ranging from 200 to 320 km/h. The optimal pre-sag (left) and the minimum σ obtained (right) are shown in Fig. 7. Looking for a smoother interaction force, it is clear that the SW catenary behaves better than the Benchmark catenary for all the studied velocities, since the optimal pre-sag is close to 0 for all the studied velocities. The Benchmark catenary gets closer to its optimal behavior at velocities lower than 270 km/h, for which the optimal pre-sag approximates to the Benchmark catenary static sag.

For both catenary models the interaction force shows higher variability, as evidenced by the clear increasing tendency of σ , as the train speed increases. On the other hand, the optimal pre-sag shows different tendencies for each catenary type. While the optimal behavior of the SW catenary is achieved with hardly any initial sag, for the Benchmark catenary, the lower the velocity the more beneficial pre-sag seems to be. According to the results, for this type of catenary a pre-sag between 1/1000 and 1/2000 of span length is optimal at velocities below 270 km/h.

The optimal σ can also be compared with respect to the ones obtained at the same train speed for both reference catenaries (see the curves with cross markers in Fig. 7b). This comparison reveals that for the SW catenary the greatest reduction in σ is only 5% at $v = 210$ km/h. This result confirms that with the presence of pre-sag there is no

observable improvement in current collection quality for this catenary with stitch wires. Conversely, the Benchmark catenary shows a wide margin of greater improvement for high train speeds. As an example, at $v = 320$ km/h, a 31.05% of σ could be reduced with an appropriate sag. Despite these results, it seems to be reasonable to seek some more appealing variables for which the dynamic behavior of the catenary system could be optimized.

6.2. Benchmark catenary optimization

The first optimization carried out for the Benchmark catenary considers Δh_{c_i} for $i = 1, \dots, N_p$ as optimization parameters. If the height of the connection point between the steady arm and the contact wire is set as a reference, Δh_{c_i} denotes the height of the contact wire at dropper point i measured from this reference, as seen in Fig. 8. The desired catenary configuration is obtained by solving the initial configuration problem (5), in which the optimization variable, i.e. the desired contact wire height, is imposed as a constraint Eq. (4) (see [17]).

Figure 8: Graphical description of the optimization variables: Δh_{c_i} and d_i .

Since every span must be equal and their symmetry has to be preserved, the number of variables of the problem amounts to $N_p = 5$. The 5 variables range from $\Delta h_{c_i}^{min} = -0.02$ m to $\Delta h_{c_i}^{max} = 0.06$ m at intervals of 1 mm. This problem is labeled as B1, and the result shown in the first row of Table 1 is obtained after 120 generations with a population of 100 individuals. A span of the B1 optimized catenary is depicted in Fig. 9, in which a non-uniform contact wire height is seen. It is important to highlight that with only changes in dropper lengths, the optimal configuration obtained produces a $\sigma_{B1} = 17.71$ N, i.e. more than 56% less than that of the reference catenary with 55 mm of pre-sag.

Figure 9: *Optimized geometry obtained from the B1 problem.*

Problem identifier	Variable type	Optimal values (m)	$\sigma(f_{inter})$ (N)	σ reduction (%)
B1	Δh_c	-0.008 -0.002 0.003 -0.012 -0.016	17.71	56.52
B2	d	3.72 9.36 15.96 22.68	34.16	16.13
B3	Δh_c	-0.002 0.001 -0.018	18.44	54.73
	d	9.8 15.8		
Reference values (m)				
B Ref.	Δh_c	0 0.024 0.041 0.052 0.055	40.73	—
	d	4.5 10.25 16 21.75 27.5		

Table 1: *Optimization results of the Benchmark catenary.*

As mentioned above, the Benchmark catenary has droppers equally spaced within a span. The second optimization problem, labeled B2, is intended to find the optimal dropper spacing for the design speed, while keeping the pre-sag or the reference model. In this case, the distance d_i between the left steady arm of the span and the dropper i are chosen as optimization variables. As in this catenary there is an odd number of droppers per span, the central dropper cannot be moved to preserve the catenary symmetry, therefore $N_p = 4$. In order to avoid overlapping and trying to find a dropper distribution as uniform as possible, the proposed range for each variable is shown in Table 2. These domains, which notably reduce the design space, are discretized into increments of 1 cm in length.

The GA stopped after 75 generations, which are composed of 80 individuals, giving the results shown in Table 1. A graphical representation of the optimized B2 catenary geome-

i	1	2	3	4
d_i^{min} (m)	0.1	7.4	13.2	18.9
d_i^{max} (m)	7.3	13.1	18.8	27.4

Table 2: Variable limits used in the B2 optimization problem.

try is given in Fig. 10. In this case $\sigma_{B2} = 34.16$ N, which represents a 16.13% of reduction when compared to the reference Benchmark catenary. Although this reduction is not as large as the one obtained in the B1 optimization, dropper spacing undoubtedly arises as an important factor in improving current collection quality.

Figure 10: Optimized geometry obtained in the B2 problem.

The question remains as to whether some droppers could be eliminated without major effects on the dynamic behavior. In order to check this scenario, we chose a Benchmark catenary with only 5 droppers per span. The B3 optimization is carried out for this new catenary with fewer droppers, consisting of optimizing both contact wire height, and dropper spacing. Thus, there are 5 optimization variables altogether, 3 heights and 2 dropper locations. The size of the population is set to 100 individuals and the limits for each variable are listed in Table 3.

i	d_i (m)		Δh_{c_i} (m)		
	1	2	1	2	3
Min.	0.1	13.1	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
Max.	13	27.4	0.06	0.06	0.06

Table 3: Variable limits used in the B3 optimization problem.

After 70 generations the optimization problem is solved, giving the optimal variables that appear in Table 1. With 4 fewer droppers per span, the optimized B3 catenary depicted in Fig. 11, offers almost the same good behavior as the B1 topology in terms of σ . For this problem, the optimal solution presents $\sigma_{B3} = 18.44$ N, which is almost a 55% lower than that obtained with the reference catenary.

Figure 11: *Optimized geometry obtained in the B3 problem.*

6.3. Stitch wired catenary optimization

In this section, the topology of the catenary with stitch wires is optimized. This catenary model has 7 droppers per span and the contact wire holds horizontally. In the first place, dropper lengths optimization is carried out, in which Δh_{c_i} , for $i = 1, \dots, N_p$, are considered as optimization variables. Again, as every span must be equal and symmetric, the number of variables in this problem is $N_p = 4$. The range of variation allowed in this case for the 4 variables is $\Delta h_{c_i}^{min} = -0.02$ m to $\Delta h_{c_i}^{max} = 0.02$ m. This problem is labeled as SW1, and the optimum is obtained after 90 generations with a population size of 80.

The result of the SW1 problem is given in Table 5 and Fig. 12. The SW1 catenary undergoes a smoother interaction force, as it is clear from $\sigma_{SW1} = 14.14$ N, than the reference SW catenary, with which a 36.6% greater σ is obtained. Comparing the SW1 configuration with the B1 optimized catenary (see Fig. 9), the main difference is observed in the height of the central point, being much lower for the Benchmark catenary type.

Figure 12: *Optimized geometry obtained in the SW1 problem.*

The second optimization concerns the search for the optimal dropper spacing in terms of current collection quality. For this case there are only 3 optimization variables d_i , since the dropper located at midspan cannot be moved to preserve the symmetry of this catenary, because again it has an odd number of droppers in each span. This problem is labeled as SW2 and the allowed ranges for each variable are shown in Table 4.

i	1	2	3
d_i^{min} (m)	0.1	9.1	20.5
d_i^{max} (m)	8.9	20.4	32.4

Table 4: *Variable limits used in the SW2 optimization problem.*

With a population of 60 individuals, after 54 generations the GA found the optimum, which can be seen in Table 5. In Fig. 13 a span of the optimized SW2 catenary is plotted. The standard deviation of the interaction force is very similar to that achieved by the SW1 configuration. Specifically, $\sigma(f_{inter}) = 14.05$ N.

The location of the three droppers near the midspan indicates the possibility of removing two of them, so that the SW3 optimization problem is carried out on a SW catenary with only 5 droppers per span. Like the B3 problem, in this case there are 5 optimization variables composed of 2 dropper locations and 3 punctual heights along the contact wire. Their ranges are listed in Table 6. Since there are 5 variables to optimize, a population of 100 individuals is set.

Figure 13: *Optimized geometry obtained in the SW2 problem.*

Problem identifier	Variable type	Optimal values (m)	$\sigma(f_{inter})$ (N)	σ reduction (%)
SW1	Δh_c	0.002 0.004 -0.009 -0.001	14.14	36.60
SW2	d	5.36 16.83 29.21	14.05	37.00
SW3	Δh_c	0.002 0.004 0	12.42	44.31
	d	6.04 18.27		
Reference values (m)				
SW Ref.	Δh_c	0	22.30	-
	d	6 15.48 24.18 32.5		

Table 5: *Optimization results of the SW catenary.*

i	d_i (m)		Δh_{c_i} (m)		
	1	2	1	2	3
Min.	2	10	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
Max.	9	30	0.02	0.02	0.02

Table 6: *Variable limits used in the SW3 optimization problem.*

The GA have only taken 85 generations to find the optimal solution shown in Table 5. In this catenary topology the three central droppers are almost equally spaced, as can be seen in Fig. 14. The dispersion of the interaction force is the lowest of the three optimized SW catenaries, with $\sigma_{SW3} = 12.42$ N. This represents a reduction of 44.31% with respect to the value obtained for the reference SW catenary.

Figure 14: *Optimized geometry obtained in SW3 problem.*

6.4. Analysis of the optimized catenaries

It is interesting to analyze some static and dynamic characteristics of the optimized catenary configurations obtained in the previous sections. Specifically, the stiffness of the catenary along with the internal force of the droppers in the static equilibrium position are explored and the dynamic behavior of the optimized catenaries, even at train speeds different to the design speed, is also investigated.

6.4.1. Static characteristics of the optimized catenaries

The stiffness, k_{st} , at a certain point in the catenary is defined as the relationship between the vertical uplift and the upward force applied thereon. Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 show this magnitude calculated in a central span subjected to a load $F = 100$ N (left) or $F = 200$ N (right) for the Benchmark and the Stitch Wired catenaries, respectively. Particularly for the former, a noticeable difference in stiffness is observed when the value of the applied force changes. This is due to the unilateral non-linearity exhibited by the droppers, which tend to slacken making the catenary to be more flexible.

Comparing the optimized catenary configurations with respect to their reference configurations, although in the SW optimized catenaries there is a reduction in the variability of the stiffness along the span, it seems more drastic in the case of B1 and B3 optimized

Figure 15: Vertical stiffness of the Benchmark catenaries.

Figure 16: Vertical stiffness of the SW catenaries.

configurations. This means a smaller difference between the maximum k_{st}^{max} and the minimum k_{st}^{min} stiffness values. In order to quantify this effect, the stiffness variability coefficient is defined as:

$$\alpha = \frac{k_{st}^{max} - k_{st}^{min}}{k_{st}^{max} + k_{st}^{min}} \quad (13)$$

This coefficient is calculated for all the eight catenaries, as shown in Table 7. For catenary B1, this reduction largely exceeds the 50%. In contrast, the optimized B2 catenary despite

showing more variability in stiffness, was demonstrated to be better in current collection quality. What emerges from these results is the benefit, although limited, of having a more uniform catenary stiffness distribution.

Cat. Label	$F = 100$ N	Reduction (%)	$F = 200$ N	Reduction (%)
B Ref.	0.431	—	0.432	—
B1	0.197	54.31	0.143	66.90
B2	0.486	-12.71	0.490	-13.43
B3	0.223	48.28	0.171	60.42
SW Ref.	0.135	—	0.135	—
SW1	0.109	19.26	0.109	19.26
SW2	0.118	12.59	0.118	12.59
SW3	0.104	22.96	0.104	22.96

Table 7: *Stiffness variation coefficient α of the optimized catenaries.*

Another aspect that requires to be analyzed is the internal force of droppers, f_d , in the static equilibrium configuration. In Fig. 17 these forces are represented for the Benchmark reference and optimized catenaries. For the reference configuration, due to the initial pre-sag, the droppers located at the ends are much more tensioned than the central ones, which are almost uniformly loaded. A similar trend is observed for B2 catenary. Conversely, more irregularity in dropper tensions is present for optimized B1 and B3 catenaries. It is also noticed that certain droppers, such as the 1st and 9th droppers in B1, are barely loaded. Similar conclusions are drawn for SW catenaries, as shown in Fig. 18.

6.4.2. Dynamic behavior of the optimized catenaries

Although the current collection quality has been quantified by means of the standard deviation of the interaction force, it is also interesting to see its time evolution. This is what is represented in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20 for the two central spans of the Benchmark and SW catenary models and their respective optimized catenaries, when the vehicle operates at the design speed. No low-pass filter has been applied to the contact force in Fig. 19, while the contact force represented in Fig. 20 has been low-pass filtered at 20 Hz. The central support is highlighted by the vertical dashed line in both figures.

For B1 and B3 catenaries, one can find lower local maxima near the supports. Additionally, higher local minima are observed near the midspan. For the SW catenaries it is more

Figure 17: *Dropper forces in static equilibrium configuration for Benchmark catenaries.*

Figure 18: *Dropper forces in static equilibrium configuration for SW catenaries.*

difficult to extract information from Fig. 19. However, the three important peaks present in the reference model are not generated in the optimized configurations.

Figure 19: *Interaction force at $v = 300$ km/h.*

Figure 20: *Interaction force low-pass filtered to 20 Hz at $v = 300$ km/h.*

Another important parameter that needs attention is the steady arm uplift. This magnitude must be controlled in order to avoid interferences with the registration arm. The vertical displacement of the central steady arm during train passage, is displayed in Fig. 21 for all the catenaries at $v = 300$ km/h. The B1 and B3 catenaries exhibit a higher steady

Figure 21: *Central steady arm uplift at $v = 300$ km/h.*

arm uplift. It should be noted that these optimized catenaries have a much lower stiffness on the supports region. Although this increased uplift is not a desired effect, the maximum displacement does not exceed the values recommended by the standards (between 100 and 120 mm). No notable differences are observed for the other optimized catenaries with respect to their reference cases.

As pointed out in Section 5, catenary optimizations are carried out only for a single train speed, which means that the optimized catenaries must be tested at other train velocities. Fig. 22 shows the standard deviation σ of the interaction force for B1, B2 and B3 optimized configurations at different speeds. These results are also compared to those obtained from the reference catenary for the same range of velocities.

Fig. 22 reveals that B1 and B3 catenaries behave similarly with respect to changes in train speed. Their interaction force not only is much less oscillatory than that of the reference catenary at the design speed, but also great improvements are achieved when the train travels at velocities greater than 240 km/h. However, at velocities below 240 km/h, these catenary configurations exhibit a quite similar performance than that of the Benchmark reference topology. On the other hand, the B2 catenary barely improves its current collection quality for the design train speed. Furthermore, at all the other studied velocities any difference is found if it is compared with the reference scenario, which makes it the least promising option.

Figure 22: *Optimized Benchmark catenaries behavior at different train speeds.*

Moving to the optimized SW catenary configurations, Fig. 23 shows their dynamic behavior in terms of σ , for the same range of train speeds. In this case, although the three optimized catenaries achieve a good improvement at the design speed, the catenary with optimized contact wire height (SW1) shows a highly oscillatory interaction force at velocities below 280 km/h. However, the SW2 and SW3 catenaries manifest a better behavior at low train speeds, although not as good as the reference SW catenary. Unlike the SW1 catenary, these two options seem to be more stable versus velocity changes, being the SW3 the most suitable solution according to this criterion. In addition, the SW3 catenary presents the lowest interaction force σ at the design train speed.

7. Conclusions

This paper describes an attempt to find optimized catenary configurations in terms of current collection quality for a given train speed, which does not guarantee better behavior at other velocities. This optimization consists in finding the catenary geometry which leads to the minimal standard deviation of the pantograph-catenary interaction force. The optimizations have been carried out by means of a Genetic Algorithm in which contact wire height (by changes in dropper lengths), dropper spacing, or even both, are set as optimization variables.

Figure 23: Behavior of the optimized SW catenaries at different train speeds.

Several optimizations have been performed for two different catenary types: with and without stitch wires. The results of the optimizations show that current collection quality can be improved by setting the appropriate contact wire height, that moderate benefits can be obtained by varying dropper spacing and that even the removal of certain droppers can be also an appealing option to be considered.

Most of the optimized catenaries show a more uniform stiffness than their respective reference catenary geometries. The largest reduction in stiffness variation along the span is achieved in catenaries B1 and B3. Indeed, these two optimized configurations show higher uplifts of their steady arms, which, although they do not exceed the recommended limits, should be controlled to avoid mechanical interferences with registration arms.

Regarding the dynamic behavior at different train speeds, the optimized catenaries do not worsen the current collection quality up to velocities far from the design one, specially for the Benchmark catenary type. Nevertheless, the optimized catenaries with less number of droppers seem to be the most consistent options in both Benchmark and Stitch wired catenary models. They exhibit a great behavior not only at the design speed, but also they are the least sensitive to changes in velocity, if compared with the other optimized catenaries.

In conclusion, the results show that not only pre-sag can be a beneficial factor in current

collection, but that catenary designers should also consider other geometric parameters such as contact wire height profile or dropper spacing within the span, because they can lead to great reductions in interaction force fluctuations. Besides, genetic algorithms emerge as a suitable tool that can be used to good effect in designing better catenaries.

Appendix A. Input data of the stitch wired catenary model

The geometric input parameters needed to define the SW catenary model are shown in Table 8.

Input parameter	Value
Span length	65 m
Pre-sag	0 m
Encumbrance	1.3 m
Messenger wire stagger	0 m
Messenger wire clamp	0.21 kg
Stitch wire length	18 m
Contact wire stagger	± 0.2 m
Contact wire clamp	0.21 kg
Steady arm length	1.15 m

Table 8: *Geometric data of the SW catenary model.*

The dropper spacing of this catenary is depicted in Table 9.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Longitudinal position of droppers (m)	6	15.48	24.18	32.5	40.82	49.52	59

Table 9: *Dropper spacing along the span.*

Table 10 gives the material properties of the different cables which form the SW catenary.

	Mass/unit length (kg/m)	Axial stiffness EA (MN)	Bending stiffness EI (Nm ²)	Tension (kN)
Messenger wire	0.864	1.042	136.09	15.75
Contact wire	1.374	1.65	238.70	31.5
Stitch wire	0.091	0.11	–	3.5
Droppers	0.091	0.11	–	–
Steady arm	1	1.1	–	–

Table 10: *Material properties of the SW catenary components.*

Finally, the values of the lumped parameters defining the model of the pantograph associated to the SW catenary are displayed in Table 11.

d.o.f.	m (kg)	c (Ns/m)	k (N/m)
1	6.6	0	7000
2	5.8	0	14100
3	5.8	70	80

Table 11: *Lumped parameters of the pantograph model for the SW catenary.*

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support received from the FPU program offered by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Spain (MECD), under grant number FPU13/04191, and also the funding provided by the Regional Government of Valencia (PROMETEO/2016/007).

References

- [1] P. Nāvik, A. Rønnquist, and S. Stichel, “The use of dynamic response to evaluate and improve the optimization of existing soft railway catenary systems for higher speeds,” *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*, vol. 230, no. 4, pp. 1388–1396, 2016.

- [2] P. Harell, L. Drugge, and M. Reijm, “Study of critical sections in catenary systems during multiple pantograph operation,” *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*, vol. 219, no. 4, pp. 203–211, 2005.
- [3] F. Kiessling, R. Puschmann, A. Schmieder, and E. Schneider, *Contact Lines for Electric Railways. Planning, Design, Implementation, Maintenance*. 2009.
- [4] S. Bruni, J. Ambrosio, A. Carnicero, Y. H. Cho, L. Finner, M. Ikeda, S. Y. Kwon, J.-P. Massat, S. Stichel, and M. Tur, “The results of the pantograph-catenary interaction benchmark,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 412–435, 2015.
- [5] A. Shabana, “Computer implementation of the absolute nodal coordinate formulation for flexible multibody dynamics,” *Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 16, pp. 293–306, 1998.
- [6] N. Zhou and W. Zhang, “Investigation on dynamic performance and parameter optimization design of pantograph and catenary system,” *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 288–295, 2011.
- [7] J.-W. Kim and S.-N. Yu, “Design variable optimization for pantograph system of high-speed train using robust design technique,” *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 267–273, 2013.
- [8] J. Ambrósio, J. Pombo, and M. Pereira, “Optimization of high-speed railway pantographs for improving pantograph-catenary contact,” *Theoretical and Applied Mechanics Letters*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 013006, 2013.
- [9] J.-H. Lee, Y.-G. Kim, J.-S. Paik, and T.-W. Park, “Performance evaluation and design optimization using differential evolutionary algorithm of the pantograph for the high-speed train,” *Journal of mechanical science and technology*, vol. 26, no. 10, pp. 3253–3260, 2012.
- [10] J.-P. Massat, C. Laurent, J.-P. Bianchi, and E. Balmès, “Pantograph catenary dynamic optimisation based on advanced multibody and finite element co-simulation tools,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 52, no. sup1, pp. 338–354, 2014.
- [11] Y. H. Cho, K. Lee, Y. Park, B. Kang, and K.-n. Kim, “Influence of contact wire pre-sag on the dynamics of pantograph-railway catenary,” *International journal of mechanical sciences*, vol. 52, no. 11, pp. 1471–1490, 2010.

- [12] W. Zhang, G. Mei, and J. Zeng, “A study of pantograph/catenary system dynamics with influence of presag and irregularity of contact wire,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 37, no. sup1, pp. 593–604, 2002.
- [13] M. L. Yu, W. Z. Liu, J. Zhang, and C. Y. Yan, “Influence of dropper spacing on quality of pantograph-catenary current collection,” in *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 654, pp. 78–81, Trans Tech Publ, 2014.
- [14] S. Koziel and X.-S. Yang, *Computational optimization, methods and algorithms*, vol. 356. Springer, 2011.
- [15] W. Hare, J. Nutini, and S. Tesfamariam, “A survey of non-gradient optimization methods in structural engineering,” *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 59, pp. 19–28, 2013.
- [16] M. Tur, L. Baeza, F. Fuenmayor, and E. García, “PACDIN statement of methods,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 402–411, 2015.
- [17] M. Tur, E. García, L. Baeza, and F. Fuenmayor, “A 3D absolute nodal coordinate finite element model to compute the initial configuration of a railway catenary,” *Engineering Structures*, vol. 71, pp. 234–243, 2014.
- [18] S. Gregori, M. Tur, E. Nadal, J. Aguado, F. Fuenmayor, and F. Chinesta, “Fast simulation of the pantograph-catenary dynamic interaction,” *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, vol. 129, pp. 1–13, 2017.
- [19] S. H. Kia, F. Bartolini, A. Mpanda-Mabwe, and R. Ceschi, “Pantograph-catenary interaction model comparison,” in *IECON 2010-36th Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, pp. 1584–1589, IEEE, 2010.
- [20] J. Gerstmayr and A. A. Shabana, “Analysis of thin beams and cables using the absolute nodal co-ordinate formulation,” *Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 45, no. 1-2, pp. 109–130, 2006.
- [21] A. Collina and S. Bruni, “Numerical simulation of pantograph-overhead equipment interaction,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 261–291, 2002.
- [22] J. Ambrósio, J. Pombo, P. Antunes, and M. Pereira, “PantoCat statement of methods,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 314–328, 2015.

- [23] EN 50367, “Railway applications. Current collection systems. Technical criteria for the interaction between pantograph and overhead line,” *European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization*, 2012.
- [24] P. Navik, A. Ronnquist, and S. Stichel, “Variation in predicting pantograph–catenary interaction contact forces, numerical simulations and field measurements,” *Vehicle System Dynamics*, pp. 1–18, 2017.
- [25] EN 50318, “Railway applications. Current collection systems. Validation of simulation of the dynamic interaction between pantograph and overhead contact line,” *European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization*, 2002.